

UDC 338.32.053.4; 677.011

WAYS OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF USAGE THE PRODUCTION CAPACITY OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES

ПУТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОЙ МОЩНОСТИ ТЕКСТИЛЬНЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ

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Abstract. The article considers the issues of increasing the efficiency of production capacities of textile enterprises, and a number of factors affecting the production capacity of textile enterprises have been studied. The purpose of this article is: to determine the essence of the production capacity of textile enterprises, to identify ways of increasing the efficiency of production capacity at textile enterprises. Recommendations given by the author can be used in industry, and the results of the systematic analysis indicated in this article can be used in writing master's theses, qualification and coursework.

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрены вопросы повышения эффективности производственных мощностей текстильных предприятий, изучены ряд факторов влияющих на производственную мощность текстильных предприятий. Целью данной статьи является: определение сущности производственной мощности текстильных предприятий, выявление путей повышения эффективности производственной мощности в текстильных предприятиях. Рекомендации предложенные автором можно использовать в промышленности, а результаты систематического анализа можно использовать в частности производстве, написании магистерских диссертаций, квалификационных и курсовых работ.

Keywords: efficiency of use, fixed assets, equipment, textile industry, production capacity.

Ключевые слова: эффективность использования, основные средства, оборудование, текстильная промышленность, производственная мощность.

Uzbekistan is one of the most densely populated country in Central Asia, as well as a major producer of cotton fiber in the post-Soviet space. Uzbekistan occupies the sixth place in the world for the production of cotton and the third - for its exports, being also an increasingly active participant in the textile market. Annually more than 1 million 250 thousand cotton fibers are produced in the republic, of which the internal volume of processing is more than 60%, while in the medium term Uzbekistan will continue to provide internal processing of cotton fiber and production of textile products up to 70%. Today Uzbekistan's light industry, in particular, the textile sector, is one of the strategically important and dynamically developing sectors of the national economy (www.legprom.uz).

In Uzbekistan, the situation in economic development has dramatically changed, the implementation of a purposeful system of state industrial policy aimed at diversifying and modernizing, increasing the competitiveness of the domestic economy, supporting the development of leading industries, including increasing their export potential through deepening the processing of

local raw materials, has begun. Consistent and systematic reorientation of exports from raw materials to finished products with high added value allowed to form a new strategy for the development of light industry, aimed at the future.

In the following years, significant results were achieved and necessary measures were taken to expand the presence of Uzbekistan's textile products in the world textile market, and the light industry became one of the leaders in the export of products with high added value. And this puts the task of increasing the production capacity in textile enterprises. Production capacity is technically, technologically, organizationally, financially-economically and socially justified norm of effective working time of the normative number of the main production personnel of the enterprise for a certain period of time. By production capacity we mean output that can be produced within a certain calendar period of time on the existing production and technical base with full load and optimal mode of its use in normal production and labor conditions. From solving the problem of increasing the efficiency of the use of basic production assets and the capacity of enterprises, the place of the enterprise in industrial production, its financial status, and competitiveness in the market depends. Any enterprise, regardless of the form of education and type of activity, must constantly consider the movement of its fixed production assets, their composition and state, and the effectiveness of their use. This information allows the company to identify the ways and reserves to improve the efficiency of the use of fixed assets, and in addition to detect and correct negative deviations in time, which in the future may entail serious consequences for the successful operation of the enterprise.

Literature review

The main methodological views were formed in the classical works of scientists A. Smith [1], N. Douglass [2] and A. Marshall [3]. Also, the issues of production funds were discussed in the scientific works of foreign scholars of economists. The most famous great contribution to the research and definition of the theory of control of production capacity was made by foreign scientists as C. J. McNair and Richard Vangermeerschand [4] R. B. Chase [5].

Scientists from the CIS countries G. Aleksandrov [6], P. G. Bunich [7], V. A. Vodyanov [8], N. L. Zaitsev [9], I. M. Petrovich [10], R. A. Fatkhutdinov [11], Ya. B. Kvasha [12], L. P. Vasilevich [13] and A. A. Balabins [14]. In their scientific works are considered the management of production capacities of industrial enterprises. Theoretical questions of management of the industrial enterprises and organizational features have been studied in the works of the scientists V. N. Privalov [15], Yu. V. Zabaykin [16] and N. B. Kaparov [17]. These problems also studied leading uzbek scientist-economists: M. Sharifkhodjaev [18], S. S. Gulyamov [19], Sh. Zainutdinov [20] and N. K. Yuldashev [21]. But reviewing of the study of these literatures indicated that the problems of improving the management of production capacities of textile enterprises and their results in the conditions of economic modernization had not been studied sufficiently deeply. The management of production capacities of industrial enterprises was relevant in all models of the economy. In the above studies and in scientific papers, insufficient attention was paid to the problem of increasing the efficiency of managing the production capacities of textile enterprises.

Methodology

The production capacity of the enterprise is characterized by the maximum quantity of products of the appropriate quality and assortment that can be produced by it in a unit of time with the full use of the basic production assets in the optimal operating conditions. The production capacity of a textile enterprise is characterized by the maximum quantity of products of the appropriate quality and assortment that can be produced by it in a unit of time with the full use of fixed production assets under optimal operating conditions.

The production capacities can be viewed from various positions, on the basis of this, the theoretical, maximum, economic and practical capacities are determined.

Theoretical (design) capacity characterizes the maximum possible output of products under ideal production conditions. It is defined as the hourly limit of the capacities of the means of labor with a full annual calendar fund of work time during the entire period of their physical service. This indicator is used to justify new projects of expansion of production, other innovative measures [22].

The maximum capacity is a theoretically possible output during the reporting period with the usual composition of the products mastered, without restrictions on the part of labor and material factors, with the possibility of increasing shifts and working days, and also using only installed equipment ready for work. This indicator is important in determining the reserves of production, the volume of products and the possibilities for increasing them.

By economic capacity is understood the limit of production, which the enterprise is not profitable to exceed because of a large increase in production costs or for any other reasons.

Practical capacity is the highest output that can be achieved in an enterprise in real working conditions. In most cases, the practical production capacity coincides with the economic one.

Unlike the project, the planned production capacity of operating enterprises is calculated based on the applied technological processes, the existing equipment park, the available production areas.

The production capacity of the enterprise is not constant, it varies in time, so it is calculated for a certain calendar date. As a rule, the power is calculated for January 1 of the planned year and January 1 of the next year for the planned period. The production capacity for January 1 of the planned year is the input capacity; Capacity of the enterprise on January 1 following the planned year - output power [23].

Main part

The increase in the efficiency of the production and economic activities of a modern enterprise largely depends on the use of its production capacities. The production capacity of an industrial enterprise is an objective technical and economic category that characterizes the maximum possible output of products at the achieved or planned level of technology, technology and production organization. From this it follows that the analysis of the use of production capacities of the enterprise plays an important role in the current conditions of management.

Production capacity determines the level of production of goods, goods and services, the degree of containment of output or the upper limit of sales of products. Ultimately, production capacity means the ability of an enterprise to produce its products within a given period of working time. Its upper limit is due to the availability of production facilities, technological equipment, labor, material and capital. The production capacity can be expressed in terms of output, mass of goods, linear quantities, rubles, man-hours and other indicators.

The definition of the enterprise's production capacity begins with the specification of the production and economic structure of individual sections and workshops and with the fixing of specific work for workplaces (equipment). At the same time, attestation is carried out to ensure that all workplaces are taken into account, identifying among them not corresponding to progressive technical, technological, organizational solutions, reducing the use of manual and heavy physical labor, as well as jobs with unfavorable working conditions, eliminating inefficient workplaces, Equipment.

Increasing the efficiency of the use of production capacity is a complex problem. It encompasses not only the issues of capital investments (investments) and the use of equipment, but also closely related to the organization, planning, technical training and production management, as well as increasing the interest of the enterprise in better use of equipment.

Fixed assets are the most stable part of the organization's assets. On the state of fixed assets and their rational use depend on the main indicators of the economic and financial activities of the organization and its financial status. From the effective management of fixed assets, the overall effectiveness of the organization's activities largely depends. For effective use of fixed assets, it is necessary to improve the management of fixed assets in order to ensure normal economic activity. At the present stage it is important to improve management in general and management of fixed capital

in particular. At enterprises, it is necessary to develop a correct, economically justified depreciation policy, which is a part of the general policy of managing fixed capital; Investment policy. The amortization policy at the enterprise should be developed taking into account the investment activity of the enterprise, the composition and structure of the fixed assets, the inflation rate, the methods of depreciation allowed by legislative and regulatory acts. It is necessary to effectively use depreciation charges as an own source of financing capital investments in fixed assets [24].

The structure of fixed capital is characterized by the specific weight of each group in the total cost of capital. The ratio between the active and passive parts of the fixed capital depends on the features of the technological process in the individual branches of activity, the level of their technical equipment. The division of fixed capital into active and passive parts is to a certain extent conditional and depends on the specific functions performed by the organization. The active part of the fixed assets includes elements that directly affect the objects of labor, allow you to control the parameters of the products. The cost of active and passive parts of fixed capital should be in such a proportion that a higher share of the active part is ensured, which contributes to the growth of production capacities, to an increase in labor productivity, to an increase in the volume of activity. In each specific case, the increase in the share of the active part should be economically justified, since the increase in the efficiency of fixed assets is ensured only when certain proportions are observed, when the increase in the share of the active part is not accompanied by a forced decrease in its level of use or deterioration of working conditions due to high density of equipment.

At the enterprise it is necessary to periodically optimize the volume, analyze the composition and structure of fixed assets, and study their dynamics. [25]. The volume optimization is carried out taking into account the potential reserves opened during the analysis of the increase in production use of operational non-current assets in the forthcoming period. Among the main of these reserves are: increased productive use of operational non-current assets over time (due to the increase in the coefficients of shifts and the continuity of their work) and increasing the productive use of operational non-current assets by capacity (due to the growth of productivity of their individual types within the technical capacity) . At the same time, it is necessary to increase the coefficient of shift and continuity of work in the event that there is an economic expediency. It is necessary to assess the condition of fixed assets. In the process of such an assessment, the following key indicators should be used: the depreciation rate of fixed assets, the asset's useful life, the intangible assets expiration rate, the intangible asset depreciation factor, and the cumulative operational efficiency of non-current assets used by the organization. It is necessary to timely and qualitatively carry out planned - preventive, current and capital repairs; To master newly introduced capacities, to acquire high-tech fixed assets in order to master new types of products, to introduce new technologies. It is necessary to free the enterprise from unnecessary, unused in production purposes machinery, equipment, vehicles by selling them or renting. It is necessary to modernize equipment, introduce new equipment and advanced technologies. In our opinion, it is important to improve the organization of labor, that is, to introduce a scientific organization of labor, which will positively affect the labor-endowment of labor, whose growth raises labor productivity. At the enterprise it is necessary to provide timely and effective updating of fixed assets as one of the stages of the fixed capital management policy. In order to ensure timely updating at the enterprise, the necessary level of update intensity is determined for each type of non-current assets in general and fixed assets in particular: the total amount of assets to be updated in the forthcoming period is calculated; Basic forms and cost of updating various groups of assets are established.

The sequence of development and adoption of management decisions to ensure the renewal of fixed assets of the enterprise is characterized at Figure 1.

Figure 1. Model of the sequence of development and adoption of management decisions to ensure the renewal of fixed assets of the enterprise (1. www.legprom.uz)

We think that the fixed capital management policy should be aimed at minimizing the loss of its value in the enterprise, since machines, mechanisms, equipment and other types of fixed assets are subject to loss of value due to obsolescence with the appearance of their more effective counterparts. It is necessary at the enterprise to improve the extensive use of fixed assets, which implies an increase in the operating time of existing equipment, as well as an increase in the quality and specific weight of existing equipment as part of equipment available in the enterprise. To characterize the extent of extensive equipment loading, the balance of its work time is studied, including: - the calendar time fund - the maximum possible equipment operation time (the number of calendar days in the reporting period is multiplied by 24 hours and by the number of units of installed equipment); - a regime time fund - the possible operating time of the equipment taking into account non-working days and the coefficient of shifts; - planned time fund - equipment operating time according to plan; It differs from the time available for finding equipment in routine maintenance and modernization, as well as standby time; - the actual fund of time worked. Comparison of actual and planned calendar funds of time allows to establish the degree of implementation of the plan for putting equipment into operation by the number and terms; Calendar and regime capability of the best use of equipment due to an increase in the coefficient of shifts, and the regime and planned - the time reserves due to the reduction of the time spent on repairs. To characterize the use of the operating time of the equipment, the following factors are used: - the calendar time fund; - a regime of time; - planned time fund; - the proportion of idle time in the calendar fund. At the enterprise it is necessary to find out whether there are any uninstalled equipment, to find out the reasons for this, then either install it, or sell it or lease it. It is important to increase the operating time of the equipment by:

- 1) constant maintenance of proportionality between production capacities of separate groups of equipment, between shops of the enterprise;
- 2) improving the maintenance of fixed assets, proper operation, compliance with production technology, avoidance of accidents, accidents;
- 3) carrying out activities that increase the share of fixed productive assets, reducing the seasonality of the enterprise in a number of industries, and extensive load of production capacities.

The main ways to improve the use of production capacity are to open up extensive and intensive reserves, as well as to raise the general educational and technical level of workers.

At textile enterprises, it is necessary to achieve the intensity of the use of fixed assets through the organization of continuous-flow production based on the optimal concentration of production of homogeneous products, the choice of raw materials, its preparation for production in accordance with the requirements of technology and the quality of the products.

The intensive way of using fixed assets also includes technical re-equipment, increasing the rate of their renewal. The experience of the textile industry shows that the rapid technical re-equipment of operating factories is particularly important for those enterprises that produce finished products, where there is more significant moral wear than physical physical assets. (The main factors are: the variability of the assortment policy due to the preferences of consumers and fashion, as well as strong competition in the international textile market.) At all textile enterprises, it is necessary to determine and analyze the indices of the provision of fixed assets (capital assets of workers in fixed assets, quantity, equipment per employee, Capacity per 1 employee, etc.) It is necessary to ensure an increase in production in 1 time, 1 equipment, 1 m² or m³ of the area, the turnover per 1 m² in warehouses for 1 m³. In large textile enterprises, where there is enough financial resources, it is necessary to carry out scientific and technical progress. At enterprises, it is necessary to analyze the efficiency indicators of the use of fixed assets: capital productivity, capital intensity, profitability of fixed assets, relative savings of funds, increase in volume products, increasing labor productivity, reducing the cost of production and the cost of reproduction of fixed assets, increasing the service life of tools, etc. In the process of analysis study the dynamics of these indicators, plan performance on their level, carried out inter-farm comparisons. Capital productivity and capital intensity are complex synthetic indicators. They depend, on the one hand, on the composition, structure, quality, rate of change in the efficiency of the use of fixed assets, on the other hand, on the rate of increase in output. Practice shows: the lower the cost of fixed assets, less wear and more share of their active part, the higher the return on assets. In different branches of the economy, the indicators of capital productivity and capital intensity are not the same. Their magnitude is influenced by the features of the economy of the sector, technology and organization, the composition and structure of fixed assets, the pace of their development, the change in the cost of reproduction of a unit of capacity. In the light industry, the return on assets is much higher than in heavy industry. The index of capital productivity characterizes the volume of production and sales of products (services) per ruble of the average annual value of fixed assets. The return on assets can also be calculated from the profit of the enterprise. Then this indicator will reflect the financial return of the funds. The index of capital productivity can be determined both for the whole mass of the main production assets of the enterprise as a whole, and for their active part. To increase the return on assets, it is necessary to increase the output and sale of products, not to allow downtime of fixed assets. Also, the return on capital is positively affected by the acceleration of turnover of circulating assets, that is, the acceleration of turnover of circulating capital has a direct impact on the size of the effect of the company's operating activities, that is, on the proceeds of the enterprise. At the enterprise it is necessary to calculate reserves of increase in output and return on assets. They can be the commissioning of uninstalled equipment, the replacement and modernization of it, the reduction of intraday and intra-shift downtime, the increase in the replacement rate, its more intensive use, the introduction of scientific and technological progress.

Figure -2. Ways to increase the efficiency of the usage of production capacities (PC) in textile enterprises (1.www.legprom.uz)

Increasing the efficiency of the usage of fixed assets can reduce the need for them (due to the mechanism for increasing the coefficients of their use in time and in capacity), since there is an inverse relationship between these two indices. Consequently, measures to improve the efficiency of the use of fixed assets can be considered as measures to reduce the need for their financing and to increase the pace of economic development of the enterprise through more rational use of its own financial resources. Increasing the efficiency of using production capacities in industrial enterprises, including textile ones, is achieved in two ways: increasing extensive and intensive use of it. (Figure -2)

More intensive use of production capacities and fixed assets is achieved, first of all, through the technical improvement of the latter. The practice of industrial enterprises shows that there is a process

of increasing the unit capacity of equipment: - the most critical parts and components are strengthened in machines, machines and aggregates; - the basic parameters of production processes (speed, pressure, temperature) increase; - Mechanized and automated not only the main production processes and operations, but also auxiliary and transport operations, often restraining the normal course of production and use of equipment; Obsolete machines are modernized and replaced with new, more advanced ones [26]. The intensity of the use of production capacities and fixed assets is also increased by improving technological processes; Organization of continuous-flow production based on the optimal concentration of production of homogeneous products; Selection of raw materials, its preparation for production in accordance with the requirements of the given technology and the quality of the products; Elimination of storming and ensuring uniform, rhythmic work of enterprises, workshops and production sites, and a number of other measures that allow increasing the speed of processing of labor items and devaluating the increase in production per unit of time, per unit of equipment or per 1 sq. km. M of production area. The intensive way of using fixed assets of operating enterprises includes, therefore, their technical re-equipment, increasing the pace of renewal of fixed assets. The experience of a number of industries shows that rapid technical re-equipment of existing factories and plants is especially important for those enterprises where there is a greater wear and tear of fixed assets. Improving the extensive use of fixed assets implies, on the one hand, an increase in the operating time of the operating equipment during the calendar period (during the shift, day, month, quarter, year) and, on the other hand, an increase in the number and proportion of operating equipment in all equipment At the enterprise and in its production link.

The increase in the working time of the equipment is achieved due to:

1) the constant maintenance of proportionality between the production capacities of individual groups of equipment at each production site, between the shops of the enterprise as a whole, between individual industries within each industry sector, between the rates and proportions of the development of industries and the entire national economy;

2) improving the maintenance of fixed assets, compliance with the technology of production, improving the organization of production and labor, which contributes to the proper operation of the equipment, avoidance of downtime and accidents, timely and quality repairs, reducing downtime of equipment in repair and increasing overhaul period;

3) carrying out measures that increase the proportion of basic production operations in the cost of working time, reduce seasonality in the work of enterprises in a number of industries, and increase the shifts in the work of enterprises.

It is known that at enterprises other than operating machines, machines and aggregates, some equipment is in repair and reserve, and some in the warehouse. Timely installation of uninstalled equipment, as well as the commissioning of all installed equipment, except for the part in the planned reserve and repair, significantly improves the use of fixed assets.

Conclusion

The main ways to improve the use of production capacity are to open up extensive and intensive reserves, as well as to raise the general educational and technical level of workers. Extensive reserves for improving the use of equipment should be used in the first place, since their involvement in production does not require large capital investments. After all, these reserves are the specific content of such a factor of increasing the economic efficiency of production, such as improving the organization of production, labor and management. First of all, it is necessary to reduce the amount of idle equipment, introduce a well-designed system of preventive maintenance of equipment, increase the shift work, especially high-performance equipment, increase the level of mechanization of assembly and installation work, improve the organization of production capacity by expanding cooperative links both intra-industry And interbranch. All these measures can lead to an increase in capital productivity, production efficiency, they are easily implemented in the production and

economic activities of the enterprise. At each enterprise there is idle equipment: it is either not yet installed, or installed, but is idle [27].

In the textile industry, an important direction to improve the use of equipment is: - Increasing the efficiency of the coefficient of change in the use of equipment, if this is economically feasible; - Exemption of the enterprise from surplus equipment, machinery and other fixed assets or leasing them; - timely and high-quality execution of preventive and capital repairs; - acquisition of high-quality fixed assets; - upgrading the level of qualification of maintenance personnel; - timely renewal, especially of the active part, of fixed assets in order to avoid excessive moral and physical deterioration; - improvement of the quality of preparation of raw materials and materials for the production process; - increasing the level of mechanization and automation of production; - providing, where it is economically feasible, the centralization of repair services; Increase concentration, specialization and combination of production; - the introduction of new technology and progressive technology: low-waste, non-waste, energy and fuel-efficient; - improving the organization of production and labor in order to reduce the loss of working time and idle time in the operation of machinery and equipment. Ways to improve the use of fixed assets depend on the specific conditions prevailing in the enterprise for a particular period of time. It is difficult to overestimate the national economic importance of the effective use of fixed assets. The solution of this problem means increasing the production of products necessary for society, increasing the output of the created productive potential and better meeting the needs of the population.

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*Работа поступила
в редакцию 09.07.2017 г.*

*Принята к публикации
11.07.2017 г.*

Cite as (APA):

Tursunov, B. (2017). Ways of increasing the efficiency of usage the production capacity of textile enterprises. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, (8), 232-242

Ссылка для цитирования:

Tursunov B. Ways of increasing the efficiency of usage the production capacity of textile enterprises // Бюллетень науки и практики. Электрон. журн. 2017. №8 (21). С. 232-242. Режим доступа: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/tursunov> (дата обращения 15.08.2017).